

CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT (CRM): POTENTIAL APPLICATION IN VETERINARY SERVICE SECTOR*

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SUMMARY: The CRM concept has initially been applied in service sector emerging in time into the business philosophy that is widely practiced through a range of activities and business branches. Establishing of a successful long-term relationship with customers is highly important aspect in modern business administration and can be successfully used in all business spheres. In modern market economy, along with the advancement of information technologies, Internet and database software programs a two-way communication between the product/service supplier and customer has been identified as the priority in business activity. Although the CRM conception still has different definitions, all the approaches are focused on client/customer satisfaction rather than to the product itself, as it was in the past. Implementation of CRM in the sphere of veterinary service would offer benefits not only to veterinary institutes, administrative and professional service departments but also to agricultural and veterinary stations and cooperatives, farmers and animal owners in a view of improved and easier communication and cooperation with the professional staff employed in the field of agriculture, veterinary medicine or food industry. CRM system database would provide a baseline for further research and analysis as well as the support to the decision-making process.

Key words: *customer relationship management, CRM concept, process.*

INTRODUCTION

The CRM (*Customer Relationship Management*) concept has been widely practiced around the globe since 20 years through all business spheres. In modern market economy, along with the advancement of information technologies, Internet and database software programs a two-way communication between the

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product/service supplier and customer has been identified as the priority in business activity. CRM conception can be defined in many ways; however, it is essentially a comprehensive approach for attracting, satisfying and maintaining the clients/customers. CRM concept relies on two basic elements – documenting and management of client/customer relationship and maintaining the database on each particular client/customer. To that aim, a wide range of data storage and management software programs has been developed. Appropriate database and well-defined procedures create a structure that enables standardization of working process, and the comprehensiveness is related not only to collecting information on the clients but to involving the entire organization into the process in a view of changing the business philosophy in the entire company and is not singled out to individual department (e.g. sales and marketing). In Serbia, this concept was first recognized by emerging small and medium enterprises and has been substantially growing since the last few years (Vidić, 2011). Thus, one can notice specialized employment advertisements looking for professionals to run the CRM in the company. Regrettably, many companies first realize the need and importance of CRM technology after they have already lost their customers. Even though CRM concept has initially been applied only in service sector, it has emerged into the business approach that is practiced through the wide range of business activities and branches.

Implementation of CRM in the sphere of veterinary service would offer benefits not only to veterinary institutes, administrative and professional service departments but also to agricultural and veterinary stations and cooperatives, farmers and animal owners in a view of improved and easier communication and cooperation with the professional staff employed in the field of agriculture, veterinary medicine or food industry. The key benefit of CRM is very simple yet highly personalized communication with clients. It enables providing animal owners with prompt and most current information on modern accomplishments in relevant field. In this way, the client obtains not only timely and high-quality service, but also the possibility to improve his production to the highest level in line with the good production practice.

The objective of this paper is to describe and understand the concept of client/customer/buyer relationship management and its potential application in veterinary practice.

DEFINITION

CRM (*Customer Relationship Management*) is a concept that primarily originates from the private sector and is related to the management of client/buyer/customer relationship (Lovreta et al., 2010). The term of CRM was first defined by mid 1990s, though the technique itself has been well known for decades and centuries back (Bergeron, 2002). Namely, manufacturers and service suppliers in the past (as well as the majority of present ones) were well aware that building of strong relationship with their clients/buyers/customers and identifying and fulfilling their wishes, habits and needs is the prerequisite and a “safe road” to business success (Anderson and Kerr, 2002). The difference is reflected by the fact that nowadays the number of clients and buyers dramatically increased and the contact and communication ways are different (mostly internet, mail or phone instead of “face-to-face” contact) thus it is impossible to know individual customers in person.

CRM concept was developed to respond to this emerging trend, and new technical and technological developments gave rise to its wide application.

Greenberg (2004) defined the CRM as „philosophy and business strategy“ that, supported by technology, strives to improve the relationship between both sides in business environment. Reynolds (2002) considers CRM not only business strategy, but also process, culture and technology“ that enables an organization to optimize the income and increase the value through „understanding and satisfying individual needs of the customer“. Anderson and Kerr (2002) define CRM as „comprehensive approach to creating, maintaining and expanding relationship with clients and customers“. In spite of a lacking unique definition of CRM, all the approaches are focused on client/customer satisfaction rather than on the product itself, as it was in the past (Kirchler et al., 2009). In that respect, nurturing of the relationship with clients based on mutual trust results in his need to share his demands, problems and ideas with the manufacturer, i.e. service supplier (Reynolds, 2002). Such an approach enables substantial savings through increased efficacy, as well as further positive effects on financial outcome (e.g. expansion of company and market, faster investment payback etc.) and increased effectiveness in achieving company’s goals (Payne and Frow 2005; Kirchler et al., 2009)

Another definition considers CRM a strategic approach aimed at creating profit for stakeholders through development of strong bonds with key customers. CRM encompasses information technology and marketing strategies to create profitable long-term relationships. CRM enables use of the data and information with an aim of understanding the clients/customers requirements and developing of marketing relations. It requires an integrated process-oriented approach of staff members, operations, processes and marketing options, which is enabled through use of novel technologies and application improvement (Payne, 2005).

ELEMENTS AND FEATURES OF CRM

Disregarding that CRM is applied in a wide range of different business branches such as banking (Ćirić, 2009), telecommunication (Kujović and Dulović, 2011) or hotel industry (Andrews, 2007), the concept itself relies on two basic elements (Kirchler et al., 2009; Anderson and Kerr, 2002).

- *documenting and managing the relationships with the client/customer* – documenting is accomplished through creation and maintaining the database on each individual client/customer. The database encompasses information on both each person and every communication with him/her. To the purpose of data storage and database management numerous software programs were developed, and collected data are appropriately stored to be readily available in relevant form and structure. In this way, the communication process is supported with actual and reliable facts and figures and still focused on single client. Mutual conversation should point out potential weaknesses that are related either directly or indirectly to the service/product in question and issues to be addressed in order to satisfy client’s needs.
- *structured and comprehensive approach*: the database and precisely defined procedures build the structure that enables the standardization of working process, which results in the improvement in efficacy and effectiveness of business activities. At the same time, the comprehensiveness does not pertain only to collecting the information on

clients but also to involvement of the entire company into the process, changing the overall company's philosophy beyond the sales and marketing department only

The main issues addressed by CRM include collecting data on customers/clients from all available and appropriate sources, storing into the data storehouse in a way that enables safe and easy access and management of the data, protection from unauthorized use and misuse, extraction of hidden information and its application in marketing activities and customer/client support (Alić, 2003). These tasks are fulfilled by the three CRM forms (Payne, 2005):

- *Operational CRM* is intended for improvement in efficacy through automating of marketing, service support and sales activities. It enters data on interactions with the customer via different databases and applications for monitoring customers' activities, yet without data processing and analysis.
- *Analytical CRM* - encompasses acceptance, storage, organizing, analysis, interpretation and usage of the data collected within the operative CRM. Highest level of integration between operative and analytical CRM is of particular importance for proper functionality of entire system (ibid). Performing of aforementioned operations within analytical CRM creates a picture of each particular client, his wishes and needs, with an aim of establishing closest possible connection and relationship with him.
- *Collaborative CRM* - deals with collaborative services and infrastructure to enable synchronization and integration of company/customer and company/its employee's interactions. Communication with clients involves a range of available communication channels (mail, phone, fax, e-mail, SMS, Web) (Dragović and Ivković, 2008). Thus, for example, the system delivers notices, offers etc. to the clients / customers and feedback is shared through the operative CRM into the system

If compared with other traditional techniques, application of CRM stands out through some unique features (Payne, 2005):

- *contact intensity*: contact with the client is at much higher level, which is mainly due to application of novel technologies and high level of automation (Payne, 2005). Novel software systems enable creation of huge number of personalized letters (the letter is highly personalized, the headline contains the name of the recipient, relevant personal data pertaining to particular recipient are automatically inserted from the database at predefined custom fields, etc.) in very short time, thus saving required manpower for this task and enabling the moving of the employees to other tasks (e.g. increasing the number of delivered letters at annual basis or performing completely different tasks). Besides the direct letters, new communication channels such as internet, e-mail, call-centers or various social networks enable frequent contacts with clients and information exchange, thus resulting in better understanding of their wishes, needs and problems. In this way, the contact is not only intense (Manić and Riznić, 2011) but also continuous and without communication gaps (see below).
- *contact continuity*: the purpose of CRM is establishing of long-term relationships with clients, which implicates high level of continuity in

interaction with customers (Parvatiyar and Jagdish 2003). CRM encompasses accomplishing and continual update of the knowledge related to client's needs, motivation and behavior as well as application of this knowledge in continuous performance improvement (service, product) by „learning from mistakes“ method (Milošević, 2006). Every communication is recorded in „contact history“ thus providing continuity in cases of personal changes in the organization-supplier, organizational reforms, etc (Parvatiyar and Jagdish 2003).

- *contact quality*: Application of CRM implies highly standardized and well-established procedures and processes that minimize potential errors and maximize client's satisfaction (Grbac and Meler, 2007). Moreover, proper implementation and application of CRM results in well trained and highly motivated employees and use of novel technologies, and hence increased quality of the contact and service support (Payne, 2005).
- *resource consumption* (time, manpower): implementing of CRM significantly reduces time required for particular activity, since: firstly, important information are stored in one base, i.e. in a „CRM data warehouse“ (Payne, 2005) thus enabling fast, easy and accurate search. Secondly, human resource savings are significantly increased due to highly automated and standardized communication with clients as well as the data processing (ibid). Thirdly, in spite of virtually high investment in software solutions (ibid), there is numerous disproving evidence to this attitude (ibid), that is, application of quite simple software solutions results in more than satisfactory outcome.
- *control and monitoring of contact intensity and quality*: highest level of data documenting as well as standardization of procedures and processes within the CRM system enables their continuous monitoring and analysis and identifying of failures, errors and potential improvements, which significantly influences the quality of every subsequent contact and service (Parvatiyar and Jagdish 2003).
- *lapse in data*: maintaining and updating of the data in a database through an intensive and continuous contact with clients is an essential aspect of CRM, which prevents potential lapse (Payne, 2005). Moreover, CRM system identifies and eliminates irrelevant and unnecessary information, thus preventing storage of lapsed or irrelevant data in the database (Domazet, 2007)
- *application of new technologies*: new developments in information technology, internet and software programs for database creation directed business activities towards the two-way communication between the organization and the client (Domazet, 2007). In that respect, the assigned username and password enable the client to enter the desired data by himself, to perform the search and communicate with the service supplier in the most appropriate way for him. Software programs that enable collecting, sending, integrating and using of processed data are the prerequisite for such communication (Grbac and Meler, 2007). Moreover, all kinds of digital content (e.g. digital cards, etc.) related to individual clients can be stored in the database and are accessible any time. For example, typing of client's name opens the whole range of information that is accessible depending on the purpose and desired details.

POTENTIAL APPLICATION OF CRM IN AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

In Serbia, this concept was first recognized by emerging small and medium enterprises and has been substantially growing since the last few years. Thus, one can notice specialized employment advertisements looking for professionals to run the CRM in the company. Regrettably, many companies first realize the need and importance of CRM technology after they have already lost their customers. However, such approach is mainly characteristic for the representative and branch offices of foreign companies in Serbia, which first establish the call-centers and then the appropriate CRM systems. Client's benefit from the implementation of CRM technology is better attention he receives from the seller / supplier. Great majority of companies in our country use tabular programs, into which they enter data on their clients. However, such data are mostly not integrated, that is, the company management has no overall insight in the system. CRM enables the overall insight in business activity through: (1) marketing communication, (2) sales communication and (3) follow-up communication within customer support (clients one has already won).

In spite that CRM concept has initially been applied in service sector, it has emerged into the business philosophy that is widely practiced through a range of activities and business branches. Implementation of CRM offers benefits not only to institutes, administrative and professional service departments but also to agricultural and veterinary stations and cooperatives, farmers and animal owners in a view of improved and easier communication and cooperation with the professional staff employed in the field of agriculture, veterinary medicine or food industry. Implementing of CRM in the aforementioned sectors would enable better monitoring and control of field conditions, which is of highly valuable for both everyday practice and science (Savić-Jevđenić et al., 2007; Vidić et al., 2008b; Boboš et al., 2013; Vidić et al., 2013). CRM system database would provide a baseline for further research and analysis as well as support to the decision-making process. This concept ensures making proper decisions, which are highly dependent on appropriate analysis of most current data on the situation in the field and actual problem of all interested parties.

APPLICATION OF CRM IN VETERINARY SERVICE SECTOR

If looking the literature sources and the spectrum of topics and branches they cover, it is apparent that CRM is mainly practiced in so called „business“ sector, particularly in the field of services such as banking, mobile telecommunications, etc. This, however, does not mean that CRM covers only a narrow spectrum of applications. On the contrary – CRM is considered a concept of unlimited application range. Previous chapter mainly addressed the CRM concept itself, and in this one, we shall consider its potential application in the veterinary service sector.

The development of marketing in veterinary practice was significantly supported by the articles published in the journal *Veterinary Economics* and numerous books published mostly in the U.S. (Ackermann, 2007). These articles and books address all issues relevant for veterinary practice, from the moment of taking decision to establish a practice and the best way to do it, everyday activities in the practice and

adjusting to variable working environment to making decision to sell the practice. In Serbia, marketing in veterinary practice has been rarely discussed issue among professionals (Vidić, 2012a). Inadequate application of marketing principles in veterinary practice is likely due to lack of knowledge as well as the necessary financial assets. In practice, the majority of veterinary organizations are reluctant to such investment (Vidić, 2012b). Since recently, veterinary practice has been considered a business requiring high quality of service since strong competition imposes the necessity of using marketing tools in order to achieve competitive advantage, survive and grow in the market (Vidić et al., 2008a).

Regardless of the reasons for practicing veterinary medicine (e.g. love for animals or other) it should be considered a business. Clients are the most important aspect of every business and it is necessary to focus on client relationships and to meet their needs (Međugorac, 2009).

Implementation of CRM in the sphere of veterinary service would offer benefits to veterinary institutes, clinics, veterinary stations and cooperatives, farmers and animal owners in a view of improved and easier communication as goods and service suppliers to animal owners. CRM would enable creation of databases that would provide a baseline for more effective veterinary services offered to end users (Vidić et al., 2008c; Savić et al., 2009). The system would contain all relevant data on the clients, particularly the following ones:

1. Data on animal owner
2. Data on organizing system
3. Number, animal species, breed/race, category
4. Purpose and extent of production
5. Number of visits to animal owner
6. Epizootiological history / anamnesis
7. Diagnoses, laboratory findings, therapy and control
8. Duration of cooperation with individual client
9. Average number of hours dedicated to the client
10. Time intervals of client's contacts / visits
11. Total turnover related to particular client
12. Fulfilling of financial obligations by the client
13. Other notices and comments of the service supplier (veterinarian)

The aforementioned data enable profile creation for each individual client and allow fully personalized subsequent access to this client (Vidić, 2012b). In practice, it means that a vet, who has hundreds of clients, can access all relevant information about individual owner, i.e. animal by one single mouse click. The vet gets an overview of all relevant data that could help him in making prompt and accurate decisions, which further results in good treatment result and satisfied client. In this way, satisfied clients get tightly bound to this veterinary organization, i.e. service supplier, which is further reflected in good financial results of the company.

The key benefit of CRM is very simple yet highly personalized communication with clients. Animal owners are provided with prompt and most current information on modern accomplishments in relevant field, seminars, education programs, possibilities of applying for various program and projects for production improvement, etc. In this way, the client obtains not only timely and high-quality service, but also the possibility to improve his production to the highest level in line

with the good production practice (Lazić et al., 2009). Successful implementation of CRM poses specific technical requirements such as integration and interconnection, safety insurance, report on system functionality, availability as well as support and upgrade.

CONCLUSION

CRM is not a novelty. Successful professionals have been applying this technique since long time ago, being aware of the fact that keeping the customer, maintaining the close relationship and personal contact with client is the key of success. Nowadays, when number of customers constantly increases, this goal is difficult to achieve; however, modern technological developments enable efficient management of customer contacts since the purpose of business is creating customers. CRM is an integrated approach for creating, maintaining an expanding customer relationships. Clients are today well educated, have access to extremely wide range of products and services offered by competitors, huge variety of information and communication possibilities thus CRM could be the solution for satisfying such clients. CRM is a philosophy and business strategy supported by technology, and is designed to improve the relationships between people in business environment. Implementation of CRM is a long-term process that is never completed, as customers' needs and requirement increase with the advancement of technology.

Establishing the relationship with clients is an important aspect of modern veterinary business, providing competitive advantage at service market. Implementation of CRM would increase and improve the relationship with clients, i.e. users of veterinary service. This would result in increased the range of services offered, improved marketing, increase in sales volume, better monitoring of sales of goods and services, faster delivery of goods and services, better quality of service aimed at customer's satisfaction.

Information on application and importance of CRM in modern business presented in this paper strongly suggest indisputable advantages of this approach that results in improvement and strengthening of links with animal owners. In spite that CRM concept has initially been applied in service sector, it has emerged into the business philosophy that is widely practiced through a range of activities and business branches. Implementation of CRM offers benefits not only to animal owners in a view of improved and easier communication and cooperation with the professional staff employed in this sector, but also to entire veterinary service sector, offering possibilities for better monitoring and control of field conditions, which is of highly valuable for both everyday practice and science. CRM system database would provide a baseline for further research and analysis as well as support to the decision-making process. This concept ensures making proper decisions, which are highly dependent on appropriate analysis of most current data on the situation in the field and actual problem of all interested parties.

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UPRAVLJANJE ODNOSIMA SA KLIJENTIMA (CRM): POTENCIJALNA PRIMENA U SEKTORU VETERINARSKIH USLUGA

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Izvod

CRM koncept je u početku bio rezervisan za upotrebu u uslužnom sektoru, ali je vremenom prerastao u poslovnu filozofiju koja je našla svoju primenu u širokom spektru aktivnosti i delatnosti. Uspostavljanje odnosa sa korisnicima usluga je veoma važan i značajan aspekt savremenog poslovanja i sa uspehom se može primenjivati u svim sferama poslovanja. U savremenoj tržišnoj privredi, paralelno sa razvojem računarske tehnologije, Interneta i softvera za kreiranje baza podataka, prioritet poslovne aktivnosti postaje dvosmerna komunikacija davaoca usluga i proizvođača i korisnika usluga i kupaca. I pored toga što jedinstvene definicije za CRM nema, zajedničko za sve njih jeste to da u fokusu imaju zadovoljnog klijenata/kupca a ne sam proizvod, kao što je to ranije bio slučaj. Koristi od implementacije CRM-a u veterinarskoj službi imali bi kako veterinarski instituti, zavodi, stručne službe, poljoprivredne i veterinarske stanice, zadruge, poljoprivredni proizvođači, vlasnici i držaoci životinja, koji bi lakše ostvarivali komunikaciju i saradnju sa stručnim licima iz svake oblasti, poljoprivredne, veterinarske, prehrambene delatnosti. Baza podataka koja nastaje stvaranjem CRM sistema postala bi polazna osnova za sve vrste ipitivanja i analiza i pružala podršku u procesu donošenja odluka. Prednost upotrebe CRM je i u veoma jednostavnoj, a visoko personalizovanoj komunikaciji sa korisnicima usluga. Na ovaj način omogućeno je da vlasnici životinja u najkraćem vremenskom periodu dobiju najaktuelnije informacije o najnovijim saznanjima iz oblasti kojom se bave. Zadovoljni klijenti postaju dugoročno vezani za veterinarsku organizaciju, odnosno davaoca usluga, što za rezultat daje i uspešno finansijsko poslovanje organizacije.

Ključne reči: upravljanje odnosima sa korisnicima usluga, CRM koncept, procesi.